

TEACHERS' PERCEPTION OF CLASSROOM OBSERVATION AND ITS PERCEIVED EFFECT ON THEIR PERFORMANCE

Hadir S. Dugaduga, Maria Chona Z. Futralan, Susana S. Austero

Foundation University, Dumaguete City, Negros Oriental Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19683834>

ABSTRACT

The study examined the teachers' perceptions of classroom observation and its effects on the teaching performance based on the Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF). It employed a descriptive-correlational survey design involving 157 grades one to six teachers from the Ginatilan and Samboan Districts, Division of Cebu. Data were collected through a standardized questionnaire and analyzed using weighted mean, standard deviation, Spearman's Rank-Order Correlation, Mann-Whitney U Test, and Kruskal-Wallis Test. The results showed that the teachers held highly positive perceptions of classroom observation in terms of its value, expectations, attitudes, and feedback effectiveness. Challenges were rated moderate, with subjectivity identified as the main concern. Most teachers received "Very Satisfactory" IPCRF ratings, while some were rated "Outstanding". No significant relationship was found between the teachers' perceptions and their performance ratings. The differences were not significant when grouped by sex but were significant when grouped according to the number of trainings attended and years of teaching experience. The findings suggest that classroom observation primarily supports professional development rather than directly influencing performance outcomes.

Keywords: *classroom observation, IPCRF, professional development, results-based performance management system, teaching performance*

INTRODUCTION

Classroom observation (CO) is a common practice in schools worldwide. It is usually conducted by the school heads, the supervisors, or the master teachers, to help develop the teachers' quality of teaching such as how they present their lessons, how they keep their students engage, and how they generally manage their classrooms, among others. It also aims to support the teachers' holistic development. In many countries, the CO is increasingly used not just for evaluation purposes but also to improve teaching, as earlier stated. Many teachers find it beneficial as it provides meaningful feedback (Unissa & Alhasan, 2024) and promotes reflective practice that supports professional growth (Ruelmann et al., 2023). Nevertheless, challenges such as the sense of bias in classroom observation often add pressure on the teachers during formal evaluations (Reyes-Chua et al., 2022). This highlights the need for clearer and more supportive observation systems focused on the attainment of the goals mentioned above.

In the Philippine context, the CO is a key component of the Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS) of the Department of Education (DepEd). It is also parallel with the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST), that provides direct evidence of classroom practices, as shown in the teachers' Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) ratings. Structured observations and constructive feedback have been shown to enhance professional skills and teaching effectiveness (Auman & Asuncion, 2023; Reños & Pontillas, 2024). However, the teachers' stress and concerns about the fairness and the consistency of the observation process highlight the need to examine how the teachers perceptions of it influence their performance.

Existing literature largely emphasizes classroom observation procedures, feedback, and performance outcomes but often overlooks the teachers' perceptions. While studies show that the teachers view classroom observation as enhancing teaching and promoting reflective practice (Fayo & Hilario, 2023; Academia et al., 2024; Torres et al., 2024), empirical evidence linking specific perception domains, such as value, expectations, attitudes, challenges, and effectiveness, to actual classroom performance remains limited, particularly in the elementary schools in the country. This study addresses this gap quantitatively by examining the relationship between the teachers' perceptions of the CO and their performance based on the IPCRF.

This research is important as it contributes to the attainment of the Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG 4), which advocates for inclusive and quality education for all. By promoting fair and effective classroom observation practices that are aligned with DepEd's goals on instructional supervision and teacher development under the RPMS and the PPST, the teachers are better supported in the improvement of their instructional practices, thereby enhancing the students' learning outcomes (Department of Education, 2025). Understanding the teachers' perceptions of being observed will guide the schools to model their observation systems to those that foster genuine professional growth. Drawing on practical teaching experience and knowledge of classroom supervision, this study aims to generate findings that will benefit the teachers, the school leaders, and the

broader education system.

Research Questions

The study aimed to determine the teachers' perception of classroom observation and its perceived effect on their performance. Specifically, it sought to answer the following problems:

1. What is the perception of teachers about classroom observation in terms of:
 - 1.1 value of observation;
 - 1.2 expectation from observation;
 - 1.3 general attitude towards classroom observation;
 - 1.4 challenges and concerns about CO; and
 - 1.5 effectiveness of CO feedback and support?
2. What is the performance of teachers based on Individual Performance Commitment and Review Forms (IPCRF)?
3. Is there a significant relationship between teachers' perception of classroom observation and their performance based on the Individual Performance Commitment and Review Forms (IPCRF)?
4. Is there a significant difference in teachers' perception about the classroom observation when grouped according to their profile in terms of:
 - 4.1 sex;
 - 4.2 number of trainings; and
 - 4.3 years of experience?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This research used the descriptive-correlational research design. It is correlational because it targeted to determine the relationship between the perceptions of the teachers regarding the CO and its perceived effect on their classroom performance. The teachers' perceptions include the value of observation, the expectations from observation, the general attitude toward classroom observation, the challenges and concerns regarding observation, and the effectiveness of the feedback and support from classroom observation of teaching. The research wanted to examine whether a statistically significant relationship exists between the teachers' perceptions of the classroom observation and their classroom performance based on the IPCRF.

Research Locale

This study was conducted in Ginatilan District and Samboan District, both under the administration of the DepEd Cebu Province Division. The districts consist of several public elementary schools. Each school is staffed with teachers who regularly undergo classroom observations as part of the RPMS. By the way, the municipalities of Ginatilan and Samboan are classified as fifth-class municipalities.

The two districts mentioned above were chosen purposively due to their manageable number of schools and their active implementation of the DepEd observation protocols. The schools are mostly located in the upland areas although there are those that are also located along the coastlines and the central area. As it is, the schools vary in size and their teaching demographics provide a diverse context for examining the teachers' perceptions of the CO and its impact on their professional performance.

This setting offered a rich environment to explore how institutional practices, community context, and teacher characteristics shape the understanding of classroom observation and its role in the teachers' professional development.

Research Respondents

The respondents are the Grades one to six public-school teachers from the various elementary schools within the Ginatilan and Samboan Districts situated in the southern part of Cebu province. It utilized cluster sampling in choosing the aforementioned districts. Subsequently, quota sampling was applied to ensure that the sample size from each district was proportionate to its population. A total of 157 teachers was proportioned to pick from both districts to ensure a balanced representation. They were chosen for their direct participation in the performance evaluations, particularly in classroom observations, for them to provide reliable insights into the perceived impact on their teaching performance.

Research Instruments

The main tool used for this study was a structured survey questionnaire adapted from the established studies by Shukri (2014) "Exploring Female Teachers' Perception towards Teacher Observation: Issues and Challenges in the Arab Context", Man (2024) "Teachers' Perception of Classroom Observation, Peer Observation as Professional Development Tool", and Unissa & Alhasan (2024) "Investigating Educators' Perspectives on Classroom Observation and the Impact of Feedback on Professional Development". Despite the diverse geographic origins of the original studies, these instruments were selected because the core components of the CO are globally standardized. The professional processes of providing feedback and evaluating teacher performance under the IPCRF are aligned with the universal pedagogical standards established in the original studies. This ensured that the measured constructs remained valid across different geographic contexts. A structured Likert-scale questionnaire was employed to gather the numerical data from the respondents.

Furthermore, the research tool was divided into three (3) parts so the respondents can focus on one topic at a time. The first part contains the disclosure statement. It is where teachers gave their consent to the researchers to collect data or information from them. Along with it is the assurance that all the data collected will be kept confidential. This part also explained the purpose of the study. The second part on the other hand is structured to obtain the teachers' profile which includes their performance rating based on the IPCRF. The purpose of the third part was to get the teachers' perception on the

CO as follows: Subscale A measured the perceived value of classroom observation; Subscale B assessed expectations from classroom observation; Subscale C captured general attitudes toward classroom observation; Subscale D identified the challenges and concerns related to classroom observation; and Subscale E determined the perceived effectiveness of classroom observation feedback and support. Each subscale consists of seven (7) items rated using a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree).

Moreover, the IPCRF used a 5-point scale: 1 = Poor, 2 = Unsatisfactory, 3 = Satisfactory, 4 = Very Satisfactory, 5 = Outstanding. The ratings reflect the teacher’s performance in lesson planning, instructional delivery, classroom management, use of materials, and student engagement. The lower scores (1–2) indicate performances that are below expectations, 3 denotes acceptable performance, while 4–5 indicate strong to exemplary classroom performance. These ratings provide a quantitative measure of instructional effectiveness that allows the analysis of its relationship with the teachers’ perceptions of the CO.

In order to establish validity and reliability, the researchers adapted scales from three prior studies and subjected them to expert review by three validators. Subsequently, a pilot test was conducted with 30 respondents. The internal consistency was measured using Cronbach’s Alpha which yielded coefficients between 0.898 and 0.960. Since all the values exceeded the 0.70 threshold, the instrument was deemed highly reliable and was approved for final administration.

The following are the results:

Variables	Cronbach’s Alpha Coefficients
Value of Observation	0.950
Expectations from Observation	0.923
General Attitude towards CO	0.898
Challenges and Concerns about CO	0.960
Effectiveness of CO Feedback and Support	0.948

Data Gathering Procedures and Analysis

The researchers secured a letter of endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School of Foundation University and obtained approval from the District Supervisors of Ginatilan and Samboan Districts, respectively. Upon the approval at the district level, an endorsement was gotten from the Schools Division Superintendent of Cebu. The researchers then sought permission from the school administrators and principals of the selected elementary schools in both districts prior to the data collection. After getting the needed permissions, the researchers proceeded with the data collection. She discussed the objectives of the research to the respondents and gave the assurance that the responses would be treated with strict confidentiality and anonymity.

To sum up, the structured survey questionnaires were then distributed personally to the respondents. They were guided as to how the questionnaire will be answered and sufficient time was also given for them to complete the survey. The researchers collected the accomplished questionnaires within an agreed period.

After the data collection, they were checked for completeness and accuracy. Appropriate Software was used to analyze the data after they were encoded and organized.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The following statistical tools were used to analyzed the data gathered from the respondents:

Mean. This was used to determine the respondent's perception regarding value, expectation, attitudes, challenges, and effectiveness of classroom observation.

Percent. Applied to describe the distribution of respondents across profile variables such as sex, years of experience, and number of trainings, as well as the proportions of performance ratings based on the IPCRF.

Standard Deviation. Calculated to measure the variability of responses around the mean for both perception domains and performance scores.

Spearman's Rank-Order Correlation. This was used to determine the connection between teachers' perceptions and their performance based on classroom observation. Specifically, it tested the relationship between IPCRF performance and the various domains of perception, including: (a) Value of Observation; (b) Expectation from Observation; (c) General Attitude towards CO; (d) Challenges and Concerns about CO; and (e) Effectiveness of CO Feedback and Support. This test was selected since the data for both perception and performance were measured on an ordinal scale.

Mann-Whitney U Test. This was utilized to check if there is a significant difference in the teachers' perception about classroom observation when they are grouped according to their profile in terms of sex. This non-parametric test was chosen as it is the most appropriate tool to compare the differences between two independent groups (male and female) when the data do not assume a normal distribution.

Kruskal-Wallis Test (H). This was utilized to determine if there are significant differences in the teachers' perception about classroom observation when they are grouped according to the following: (a) Number of Trainings and (b) Years of Experience. This test was selected as the non-parametric alternative to the One-Way ANOVA to compare the medians of multiple independent groups.

All the statistical computations were performed using statistical software such as the JAMOVI and Microsoft Excel.

The following interpretations were applied by the researchers to determine the value,

expectation, attitudes, challenges and effectiveness of classroom observation:

Score	Verbal Description	Explanation
5	Strongly Agree	The respondent fully agrees with the statement; the value, expectation, attitude, or feedback is very evident and consistently experienced.
4	Agree	The respondent generally agrees with the statement; the aspect is evident and regularly experienced.
3	Moderately Agree	The respondent remains neutral; the aspect may be moderately experienced or unclear.
2	Disagree	The respondent generally disagrees with the statement; the aspect is rarely experienced or lacking.
1	Strongly Disagree	The respondent completely disagrees with the statement; the aspect is not experienced at all or is ineffective.

To identify the degree of relationship between two variables, the researchers will apply the following descriptions (Statistical Correlation, 2009):

	Value of r	Strength of Relationship
Between	± 0.50 to ± 1.00	\pm strong relationship
Between	± 0.30 to ± 0.49	\pm moderate relationship
Between	± 0.10 to ± 0.29	\pm weak relationship
Between	± 0.01 to ± 0.09	\pm very weak relationship

Scope of the Study

The research focused only on the teachers from Ginatilan District and the Samboan District in the Division of Cebu. It determined their perceptions of the CO and its perceived effect on their performance. Specifically, it examined the teachers' perceptions in terms of its value, their expectations from the observation process, and their general attitude towards it. Additionally, the study also examined the challenges and concerns related to the CO, the effectiveness of its feedback and support, and its perceived effect on their performance.

The study also assessed the how the respondents perform based on the IPCRF and the determined the relationship between the teachers' perceptions of the CO and their performance. In addition, it investigated whether there are significant differences in the teachers' perceptions of the classroom observation when they are grouped according to selected profile variables, namely sex, the number of trainings attended, and the years of teaching experience.

Limitations of the study

This study is limited to the teachers from the Ginatilan and Samboan Districts and may not reflect the experiences in other contexts. Data were collected through an adapted,

validated self-reported questionnaire which assessed how the teachers understand the classroom observation on value, expectations, attitudes, challenges, and feedback effectiveness of the CO and the performance based on the IPCRF. The responses may have been affected by social desirability or personal bias. Also, the researchers were not able to achieve 100% retrieval of the accomplished questionnaires due to some factors. The non-returned questionnaires and the voluntary participation may have limited the sample size and the diversity of the responses. Another thing, the study did not include the perspectives of the administrators or peers, nor account for contextual factors such as resources, workload, or student behavior. Finally, the quantitative design restricts the exploration of the emotional and situational aspects of the teachers' perceptions, which a qualitative method could have addressed.

RESULTS

Table 1.1 reveals that the teachers hold a very positive perception of the value of classroom observation. This is reflected by the composite mean of 4.60, which is verbally described as "Strongly Agree" with a standard deviation of 0.65.

Table 1.1
Perception of Teachers about the Value of Classroom Observation (n=157)

Indicators	\bar{x}	VD
1. I believe classroom observations help me identify areas for professional growth.	4.68	SA
2. I believe feedback from classroom observations enhances my teaching strategies.	4.67	SA
3. I believe classroom observations provide valuable insights into my instructional practices.	4.64	SA
4. I believe classroom observations improve teaching quality.	4.61	SA
5. I believe classroom observations encourage self-reflection on my teaching methods.	4.57	SA
6. I believe classroom observations are beneficial for student learning outcomes.	4.52	SA
7. I believe classroom observations support my overall professional development.	4.50	SA
Composite	4.60	SA
SD	0.65	

Note: Verbal Description (VD); 4.21-5.00, Strongly Agree (SA); 3.41-4.20, Agree (A); 2.61-3.40, Moderately Agree (MA); 1.81-2.60, Disagree (D); 1.00- 1.80, Strongly Disagree (SD)

Table 1.2 indicates that the teachers' expectations from classroom observation are consistently rated as "Strongly Agree", with a composite mean of 4.57 and a standard deviation of 0.65.

Table 1.2
Expectation of Teachers from Classroom Observation (n=157)

Indicators	\bar{x}	VD
1. I expect classroom observations to align with my professional development goals.	4.62	SA
2. I expect to receive timely feedback after classroom observations.	4.60	SA
3. I expect to receive constructive feedback from classroom observations.	4.59	SA
4. I expect classroom observations to be conducted in a supportive manner.	4.59	SA
5. I expect classroom observations to focus on both strengths and areas for improvement.	4.55	SA
6. I expect to receive actionable suggestions after classroom observations.	4.54	SA
7. I expect classroom observations to consider the context of my classroom environment.	4.50	SA
Composite	4.57	SA
SD	0.64	

Note: Verbal Description (VD); 4.21-5.00, Strongly Agree (SA); 3.41-4.20, Agree (A), 2.61-3.40, Moderately Agree (MA); 1.81-2.60, Disagree (D); 1.00- 1.80, Strongly Disagree (SD)

Table 1.3 illustrates that the teachers' overall attitude towards classroom observation is positive with a composite mean of 4.24 and a standard deviation of 0.81. This is verbally described as "Strongly Agree".

Table 1.3
General Attitude of Teachers towards Classroom Observation (n=157)

Indicators	\bar{x}	VD
1. I am open to receiving feedback from classroom observations.	4.59	SA
2. I believe classroom observations provide a fair assessment of my teaching.	4.41	SA
3. I view classroom observations as a collaborative process.	4.38	SA
4. I trust the professionalism of observers during classroom observations.	4.32	SA
5. I see classroom observations as opportunities for growth.	4.31	SA
6. I feel comfortable being observed while teaching.	3.86	A
7. I feel excited about classroom observations.	3.81	A
Composite	4.24	SA
SD	0.81	

Note: Verbal Description (VD); 4.21-5.00, Strongly Agree (SA); 3.41-4.20, Agree (A), 2.61-3.40, Moderately Agree (MA); 1.81-2.60, Disagree (D); 1.00- 1.80, Strongly Disagree (SD)

Table 1.4 indicates that the teachers' perceptions of challenges and concerns regarding classroom observation yield a composite mean of 3.26 which is verbally described as "Moderately Agree". It has a standard deviation of 1.17.

Table 1.4***Challenges and Concerns of Teachers about Classroom Observation (n=157)***

Indicators	\bar{x}	VD
1. I am concerned that classroom observations may be subjective.	3.49	A
2. I am concerned that observations may not capture my usual teaching practices.	3.35	MA
3. I am concerned about the frequency of observations that might be excessive.	3.31	MA
4. I feel that observations add to my workload.	3.29	MA
5. I feel that observations may overlook student diversity.	3.28	MA
6. I am concerned that observations may negatively affect my performance evaluation.	3.09	MA
7. I find the observation criteria unclear.	3.02	MA
Composite	3.26	MA
SD	1.17	

Note: Verbal Description (VD); 4.21-5.00, Strongly Agree (SA); 3.41-4.20, Agree (A); 2.61-3.40, Moderately Agree (MA); 1.81-2.60, Disagree (D); 1.00- 1.80, Strongly Disagree (SD)

Table 1.5 demonstrates that the teachers strongly agreed on the effectiveness of the classroom observation feedback and support. This is proven by the composite mean of 4.34 and a standard deviation of 0.73.

Table 1.5***Perception of Teachers on the Effectiveness of Classroom Observation Feedback and Support (n=157)***

Indicators	\bar{x}	VD
1. I believe feedback from classroom observations leads to improvements in my teaching.	4.44	SA
2. I believe feedback discussions are conducted in a constructive manner.	4.38	SA
3. I believe my institution supports me through classroom observation feedback.	4.35	SA
4. I believe the feedback I receive from classroom observations is specific and actionable.	4.32	SA
5. I believe the feedback process is transparent and fair.	4.31	SA
6. I believe I have access to resources to address areas for improvement identified in observation feedback.	4.30	SA
7. I believe I receive sufficient support to implement observation feedback.	4.28	SA
Composite	4.34	SA
SD	0.73	

Note: Verbal Description (VD); 4.21-5.00, Strongly Agree (SA); 3.41-4.20, Agree (A); 2.61-3.40, Moderately Agree (MA); 1.81-2.60, Disagree (D); 1.00- 1.80, Strongly Disagree (SD)

Table 1.6 is the summary table of the perception of teachers about classroom observation. It shows that the teachers generally hold a positive perception of classroom observation.

Table 1.6
Perception of Teachers about Classroom Observation (n=157)

Indicators	\bar{x}	VD	SD
1. Value of Observation	4.60	SA	0.65
2. Expectation from Observation	4.57	SA	0.64
3. General Attitude Towards Classroom Observation	4.24	SA	0.81
4. Challenges and Concerns about CO	3.26	MA	1.17
5. Effectiveness of CO Feedback and Support	4.34	SA	0.73

Note: Verbal Description (VD); 4.21-5.00, Strongly Agree (SA); 3.41-4.20, Agree (A), 2.61-3.40, Moderately Agree (MA); 1.81-2.60, Disagree (D); 1.00- 1.80, Strongly Disagree (SD)

Table 2 reflects the performance of the teachers based on the IPCRF ratings with a mean of 4.320 and a standard deviation of 0.22.

Table 2
Performance of Teachers based on IPCRF

Rating	Adjectival Rating	F	%	Mean	SD
4.500-5.000	Outstanding	19	12.10		
3.500-4.499	Very Satisfactory	138	87.90	4.320	0.22
2.500-3.499	Satisfactory	---	---		
1.500-2.499	Unsatisfactory	---	---		
Below 1.499	Poor	---	---		
Total		157	100		

Table 3 presents the relationship between the teachers' perception of the classroom observation and their performance based on the IPCRF. Spearman's Rank-Order Correlation is utilized at 5% level of significance.

Table 3
Relationship between Teachers' Perception of Classroom Observation and Their Performance based on the IPCRF (n=157)

IPCRF performance and perception on...	r_s	p	Decision	Remark
• Value of Observation	.055	.359	Fail to reject H_{o1}	Not significant
• Expectation from Observation	.014	.815	Fail to reject H_{o1}	Not significant
• General Attitude towards CO	.071	.209	Fail to reject H_{o1}	Not significant
• Challenges and Concerns about CO	.016	.768	Fail to reject H_{o1}	Not significant
• Effectiveness of CO Feedback & Support	.027	.639	Fail to reject H_{o1}	Not significant
• Overall	.041	.451	Fail to reject H_{o1}	Not significant

Note: Spearman's Rank-Order Correlation at 0.05 Level of Significance

Table 4 is on the differences in the teachers' perception of classroom observation when they are grouped according to their profile variables, namely: sex, number of trainings attended, and years of teaching experience. Mann-Whitney U Test and Kruskal-Wallis Test are used at 5% level of significance.

Table 4
Difference in Teachers' Perception about the Classroom Observation when Grouped according to Their Profile (n=157)

Variables	Median	Comp. Value	<i>P</i>	Decision	Remark
Sex					
Male	3.97	<i>U</i> = 704	0.068	Fail to reject H_{o2}	Not significant
female	4.20				
No. of Trainings					
1 – 4	4.40	<i>H</i> = 7.693	0.021	Reject H_{o2}	Significant
5 – 8	3.94				
≥ 9	4.20				
Post-Hoc Analysis (DSCF Pairwise Comparison)					
1-4 vs. 5-8: <i>p</i> = 0.049 (significant)					
1-4 vs. ≥ 9: <i>p</i> = 0.619 (not significant)					
5-8 vs. ≥ 9: <i>p</i> = 0.110(not significant)					
Yrs. of Experience					
1 – 10	4.20	<i>H</i> = 9.599	0.008	Reject H_{o2}	Significant
11 – 20	4.19				
≥ 21	3.90				
Post-Hoc Analysis (DSCF Pairwise Comparison)					
1-10 vs. 11-20: <i>p</i> = 0.961 (not significant)					
1-10 vs. ≥ 21: <i>p</i> = 0.009 (significant)					
11-20 vs. ≥ 21: <i>p</i> = 0.043 (significant)					

Note: Mann-Whitney U Test and Kruskal-Wallis Test (H) at 0.05 Level of Significance

DISCUSSION

From the data gathered in the study, the following salient findings are hereby presented:

1. Perception of Teachers

1.1 Value of Classroom Observation

Table 1.1 reveals that the highest-rated indicator is the belief that classroom observation helps teachers identify areas for professional growth (\bar{x} = 4.68) which indicates that the teachers perceived observations as instrumental in highlighting specific areas for improvement. This finding is aligned with the studies showing that observing classroom interactions enables teachers to recognize their strengths and weaknesses and supports their long-term professional growth (Reños & Pontillas, 2024).

Significantly, the table also shows that the teachers “strongly agree” that feedback from classroom observations enhances one’s teaching strategies (\bar{x} = 4.67). This underscores the central role of the feedback in instructional improvement. Research affirms that constructive feedback, when paired with reflection and actionable suggestions, strengthens instructional decision-making, boosts teacher confidence, and informs the

application of more effective strategies in subsequent lessons (Unissa & Alhasan, 2024).

Moreover, the teachers “strongly agree” that the classroom observations provide valuable insights into the teaching practices ($\bar{x} = 4.64$). This suggests that observations make instructional approaches more visible and subject to critical examination. This indicates that by clarifying the connection between teaching strategies, student engagement, and learning outcomes, classroom observation supports reflective practice and continuous professional development (Man, 2024).

Similarly, the results indicate that the teachers “strongly” believe that classroom observations improve the teaching quality ($\bar{x} = 4.61$). This is a reflection of their perception of the observation as a mechanism for enhancing instructional standards. Empirical evidence shows that regular observation and feedback cycles contribute to an improved instructional quality and a greater alignment with professional standards coupled with frequent and specific feedback which facilitates meaningful improvements in the classroom practice (Obiso & Empiales, 2025).

In addition, the table reflects that the teachers hold a “strong” belief that classroom observations encourage self-reflection on their teaching methods ($\bar{x} = 4.57$). This finding confirms the central role of self-reflection as a core component of professional learning, wherein observation-generated data serve as concrete evidence for critically analyzing instructional practices. Consequently, such reflective processes enable the teachers to make informed adjustments and adopt more effective pedagogical strategies (Bhagwandhin et al., 2025).

Furthermore, the teachers “strongly agree” that classroom observations positively influence student learning outcomes ($\bar{x} = 4.52$). Although the direct relationship continues to be examined, existing research indicates that feedback derived from observations motivates the teachers to refine their instructional practices, which in turn can indirectly enhance student engagement and academic performance (Murphy Odo, 2022).

Finally, the teachers affirm that classroom observations significantly support their overall professional development ($\bar{x} = 4.50$). This underscores the importance of structured observation cycles, reflective practices, and professional dialogue as essential components of effective professional learning systems. Such processes collectively contribute to sustained teacher growth and continuous instructional improvement (Poulou et al., 2023; Thida & Yang, 2026).

Overall, the findings indicate that the teachers perceived classroom observation not merely as an administrative requirement but as a meaningful and integral mechanism for enhancing teaching quality, fostering reflective practice, and supporting continuous professional growth, while also promoting a culture of collaboration and ongoing feedback that empowers teachers to refine their instructional practices over time.

1.2 Expectation of Teachers from Classroom Observation

Table 1.2 unveils that the teachers demonstrate a particularly strong expectation that observations align with their professional development goals ($\bar{x} = 4.62$) which indicates that they perceived observations not merely as evaluative measures but as opportunities for reflection and instructional enhancement, especially when feedback is constructive and linked to growth objectives (Herrano, 2025).

The table also points out that the teachers expect to receive timely feedback after the classroom observations ($\bar{x} = 4.60$). Prompt feedback is considered more relevant and actionable as it enables the teachers to reflect on their practice while the experience is fresh. Such timeliness fosters meaningful dialogue, identifies areas for improvement, and connects observation outcomes directly to the classroom practice (Aljabri, 2024; Tarusha & Bushi, 2024).

The teachers also expressed strong expectations regarding the nature of feedback which in a way emphasizes the importance of constructive comments and supportive observation processes ($\bar{x} = 4.59$). Such supportive feedback, when embedded within a collaborative observation culture, transforms evaluations from mere performance assessments into meaningful tools for professional growth. In this context, observers are expected to provide guidance that fosters critical reflection while maintaining a non-threatening environment focused on continuous instructional improvement (Pantoja & Villocino, 2025).

Furthermore, the teachers strongly expect that classroom observations highlight both strengths and areas for improvement ($\bar{x} = 4.55$). Structured observation tools facilitate self-assessment and reflection that enable the teachers to recognize effective practices while identifying areas requiring enhancement. This underscores the developmental, rather than the purely evaluative, purpose of classroom observation (Caranyagan & Loquere, 2025).

The teachers also indicated a strong expectation to receive actionable suggestions following observations ($\bar{x} = 4.54$). This aligns with the findings of Seron et al. (2024), which reported that the elementary school teachers in Southern Leyte linked feedback and suggestions from observations directly to professional growth. The respondents noted that such feedback allowed them to refine their teaching practices, to adopt more creative strategies, and to enhance their instructional effectiveness.

Lastly, the teachers strongly agreed that the classroom observations should consider the context of their specific classroom environment ($\bar{x} = 4.50$). Research highlights that observation systems are most effective when adapted to local conditions and instructional realities. Senden et al. (2025) found that even well-designed tools require contextual adjustment to accurately reflect teaching quality. This underscores the necessity for observation frameworks to be flexible and tailored rather than standardized.

Generally, these findings suggest that the teachers prioritized the developmental

purpose of classroom observation and expected processes that are supportive, context-sensitive, and focused on actionable improvements rather than punitive evaluation.

1.3 General Attitude of Teachers towards Classroom Observation

Table 1.3 illustrates that the teachers are particularly receptive to receiving feedback from observations ($\bar{x} = 4.59$) which emphasizes that it is valued as a tool for reflection and instructional improvement. This indicates that the teachers perceived observations as supportive mechanisms for professional growth rather than merely evaluative tools. This is also consistent with the findings of the study of Bajec (2025).

Meanwhile, the table also divulges that the teachers strongly believed that classroom observations provide a fair assessment of their teaching ($\bar{x} = 4.41$). This is aligned with the findings of some researches which indicate that the teachers regard observations as more credible than other evaluative measures, such as the student learning objectives, and view them as effective tools for assessing teaching performance and guiding professional development (Fan, 2022).

It is likewise presented in the same table that the teachers also strongly agree that classroom observations function as a collaborative process ($\bar{x} = 4.38$). Studies on peer and reciprocal observation demonstrate that mutual feedback and reflection among teachers foster professional growth, shared knowledge, and enhanced instructional practices (Flores et al., 2025).

The table also similarly discloses that the teachers have a strong trust in the fairness and professionalism of observers during classroom observations ($\bar{x} = 4.32$). Torres et al. (2024) reported that honesty, confidentiality, and respectful feedback from observers strengthen the teachers' trust and reinforce the perception of observations as supportive rather than punitive.

Subsequently, the teachers perceived the classroom observations as significant opportunities for professional growth ($\bar{x} = 4.31$). Complementing these quantitative findings, qualitative insights indicate that experienced teachers often transition from initial anxiety to viewing observations as valuable opportunities for reflection and improvement (Academia et al., 2024).

Although comfort ($\bar{x} = 3.86$) and excitement ($\bar{x} = 3.81$) during observation are rated slightly lower, they still remain within the "Agree" range. This suggests that being observed may elicit mixed emotions, including stress and nervousness, even when the teachers acknowledged the process's professional benefits (Sadia & Dioso, 2024).

Collectively, the findings indicate that the teachers valued and accepted classroom observation as a meaningful component of their professional practice. While some apprehension or anxiety may arise due to the pressure to perform and meet expectations, these concerns do not diminish the perceived benefits, as teachers

continue to regard observations as constructive processes that support instructional improvement, reflection, and ongoing professional development.

1.4 Challenges and Concerns of Teachers About Classroom Observation

Table 1.4 indicates that the most prominent concern of the teachers is the perceived subjectivity of classroom observations ($\bar{x} = 3.49$). This suggests that the teachers are attentive to fairness and consistency in observation practices. Research shows that when the observation criteria are applied inconsistently or ambiguously, the teachers may perceive the results as biased rather than constructive for instructional improvement (Dorji et al., 2025).

It is likewise evident in the table that the teachers “moderately agree” they are concerned about whether observations capture their usual teaching practices ($\bar{x} = 3.35$). This aligns with studies indicating that educators often question the extent to which observation processes reflect authentic classroom routines. The teachers may feel that observed lessons, particularly during scheduled observations, differ from their normal teaching practices. Observations can generate stress and disrupt typical classroom dynamics which might potentially make the lessons less representative of the teachers’ everyday instruction (KhedrupLa & Karma, 2025).

The teachers also expressed moderate concern regarding the frequency of observations. They perceived them as potentially excessive ($\bar{x} = 3.31$). Research suggests that repeated or rigid observation schedules can heighten anxiety, especially when observations are framed more as evaluative measures rather than as supportive opportunities for professional development (Herrano, 2025).

Meanwhile, the teachers “moderately agree” that the classroom observations may contribute to increased workloads ($\bar{x} = 3.29$). They often entail additional preparation, documentation, and follow-up tasks, which can add to the teachers’ responsibilities. Studies indicate that these extra demands contribute to stress, particularly when they interfere with core teaching duties (Wang et al., 2025).

It is further stipulated that teachers moderately agree that classroom observations may overlook student diversity ($\bar{x} = 3.28$). This suggests a concern that standard observation tools may not fully capture inclusive teaching practices or differentiated instruction. Research emphasizes that unless observation frameworks explicitly incorporate indicators of diversity, they may fail to recognize how teachers address the varying learning needs of the students (Darwish et al., 2025).

The teachers also moderately agreed that classroom observations may negatively influence performance evaluations ($\bar{x} = 3.09$). Specifically, when observations are closely tied to appraisal or ranking systems, the teachers may experienced increased pressure, which can adversely affect their natural teaching performance (Gaines et al., 2025). This finding illustrates the importance of framing observations primarily as developmental tools rather than solely evaluative measures to mitigate stress and

support authentic instructional practices.

The data also further shows that the teachers “moderately agree” that the observation criteria are unclear ($\bar{x} = 3.02$). This indicates an uncertainty about how their teaching is assessed. Unclear criteria can create confusion, reduce the perceived value of feedback, and limit the teachers’ understanding of how observations support professional growth. This is noted in the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development-Teaching and Learning International Survey (OECD-TALIS) report (OECD, 2020).

Altogether, the findings suggest that while teachers generally accept classroom observation, they maintained moderate concerns regarding fairness, workload, clarity of criteria, and the potential impact on evaluations. These results underscore the importance of establishing clear, transparent, and consistent observation procedures to reinforce the teachers’ trust and effectively support professional development. Moreover, addressing these concerns can help ensure that classroom observations are perceived not as evaluative threats but as meaningful opportunities for growth and reflective practice.

1.5 Perception of Teachers on The Effectiveness of Classroom Observation Feedback and Support

Table 1.5 demonstrates that the teachers particularly believed that feedback will lead to improvements in teaching ($\bar{x} = 4.44$). This finding reflects recent research results which indicate that post-observation feedback is a key driver of instructional enhancement. Obiso & Empiales (2025) emphasized that constructive and supportive feedback encourage the teachers to adjust their practices and become more student-focused.

As indicated in the table, the teachers strongly agreed that feedback from classroom observations contribute to the teaching improvements ($\bar{x} = 4.38$). This aligns with the studies in Russian schools, where feedback were found to help the teachers reflect critically on their instruction and identify those areas that need improvement (Kholmanskaia, 2025). Engaging with observation feedback enables the teachers to recognize specific aspects of their teaching that require refinement.

The teachers also strongly agreed that their institutions provide support through classroom observation feedback ($\bar{x} = 4.35$). Structured feedback combined with reflective practices strengthens the teachers’ ability to refine instructional approaches. This was highlighted by Anggrainy et al. (2024). Institutional backing enhances the effectiveness of feedback and promotes professional development.

Meanwhile, it is further exhibited in the table that the teachers perceived the feedback they received as specific and actionable ($\bar{x} = 4.32$). Research shows that feedback are most effective when they clearly identify the teaching practices and provide concrete suggestions for improvement (Poulou et al., 2023). Such clarity enables the teachers to understand precisely what to improve and how to implement changes in their classrooms.

The teachers also strongly agreed that the feedback process is transparent and fair ($\bar{x} = 4.31$). Studies demonstrated that clear criteria and well-explained results build trust in the feedback process. Such, reinforces the perceptions of fairness and objectivity (Mir et al., 2023). Transparency ensures that the teachers view observations as equitable and constructive.

Also, as illustrated in the table, the teachers strongly agreed they have access to resources to address areas for improvement identified in the observation feedback ($\bar{x} = 4.30$). Evidence from Thailand shows that professional development and training opportunities helped the teachers effectively apply feedback in their teaching practice (Phusrisom & Satisampanno, 2024). Availability of resources enables the teachers to act on feedback more efficiently.

Moreover, the teachers strongly agreed that they received sufficient support to implement observation feedback ($\bar{x} = 4.28$). Research results from Japan indicated that guides, lesson examples, and mentoring assist teachers in translating feedback into practice which in turn enhanced their confidence in instructional improvement (Sawada, 2024). Adequate support ensures that feedback lead to meaningful changes in teaching.

In general, the findings indicate that the teachers perceived classroom observation feedback as constructive, fair, and well-supported. When they are clear, actionable, and backed by institutional resources, the teachers are more likely to utilize them to enhance teaching effectiveness and to promote student learning. The prior statement hence demonstrates that classroom observation serves as both an evaluative and developmental tool for professional growth.

1.6 Summary Table of the Perception of Teachers about Classroom Observation

Table 1.6 shows that the teachers generally hold a positive perception of classroom observation. The value of observation ($\bar{x} = 4.60$, $SD = 0.65$) and the expectation from observation ($\bar{x} = 4.57$, $SD = 0.64$) are both rated “Strongly Agree” which indicate that the teachers highly recognized the importance of classroom observation and expected it to contribute to their professional growth. The low standard deviations suggest consistency in the teachers’ responses.

The general attitude towards classroom observation also received a “Strongly Agree” rating ($\bar{x} = 4.24$, $SD = 0.81$). This is a reflection of their overall positive disposition toward being observed, although the responses show slightly more variations. This positive attitude appears to be closely linked to the perceived usefulness of feedback as the teachers who viewed observations favorably are more likely to engage constructively with the post-observation recommendations. The effectiveness of the classroom observation feedback and support was likewise rated “Strongly Agree” ($\bar{x} = 4.34$, $SD = 0.73$). This, too, indicates that the teachers perceived post-observation feedback as helpful and supportive in improving instructional practices.

However, in contrast, the challenges and concerns about classroom observation

obtained the lowest mean ($\bar{x} = 3.26$, $SD = 1.17$) with a verbal description of “Moderately Agree”. What this suggests is that the teachers acknowledged the presence of some concerns, such as anxiety or pressure, during observations. The higher variability of responses implies differing experiences among the teachers.

Thus, the results indicate that while the teachers strongly valued classroom observation and view it as beneficial, there remain moderate concerns that need to be addressed to further improve the observation process and make it more supportive and developmental.

2. Performance of Teachers based on Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF)

Table 2 reflects that the majority of the teachers (87.90%) obtained a “Very Satisfactory” rating, while 12.10% achieved an Outstanding rating. The computed mean performance rating of 4.32, with a low standard deviation of 0.22, suggests that the teachers generally demonstrated a high and consistent teaching performance. This indicates that regardless of individual differences, the teachers were able to meet, and even to exceed, the expected performance standards during the classroom observations. This shows that most teachers met what are expected from them in class. The small difference between scores means the teaching quality is mostly the same across all the teachers observed.

3. Relationship between Teachers’ Perception of Classroom Observation and Their Performance based on the Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF)

Table 3 presents that all computed r_s -values ranged from .014 to .071, with corresponding p -values ranging from .209 to .815, all of which are greater than the level of significance (.05). Thus, the null hypothesis is not rejected across all perception indicators, which include the value of observation, expectations, general attitude, challenges and concerns, and effectiveness of feedback and support, as well as the overall perception. This indicates that the teachers’ perceptions of the classroom observation do not have a statistically significant relationship with their teaching performance.

However, non-significance does not imply irrelevance. While the relationship may not reach statistical significance, the teachers’ perceptions can still hold practical significance by influencing engagement, motivation, and professional growth. This distinction between statistical and practical significance suggests that a lack of measurable correlation does not diminish the value of observation in fostering reflective teaching practices. This further suggests that the teachers are able to demonstrate consistent performance regardless of how they perceived the classroom observation process. Several studies show that the teachers often view classroom observation positively for professional growth, but these perceptions do not necessarily affect actual performance. Researches from Saudi Arabia, Vietnam, and even from the Philippines indicated that while the teachers value feedback and see observation as important, these

positive views are linked more to perceived growth than to measurable performance improvements (Unissa & Alhasan, 2024; Man, 2024; Reños & Pontillas, 2024; Acar et al., 2023). This suggests that the teachers' attitudes toward observation mainly influence their sense of professional development rather than their teaching outcomes. It also highlights that effective teaching depends more on the teachers' skills, experiences, and preparations than on how they feel about being observed. Consequently, the teachers can maintain high-quality instruction even if they experienced anxiety, nervousness, or indifference during the observation process.

5. Difference in Teachers' Perception About the Classroom Observation when Grouped according to Their Profile

Table 4 reflects that in terms of sex, the Mann–Whitney U test yields a computed value of $U = 704$ with a p-value of .068, which is greater than .05. Thus, the null hypothesis is not rejected. This is an indication that there is no significant difference in the teachers' perception of classroom observation between the male and the female teachers. It however suggests that the male and the female teachers generally view observation activities in similar ways. This aligns with some broader researches which indicated that gender does not always yield large differences in teacher attitudes regarding instructional evaluation processes (Satur et al., 2024).

With respect to the number of trainings attended, the Kruskal–Wallis test produces an H value of 7.693 with a p-value of 0.021, which is less than 0.05. This finding leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis. This result indicates a significant difference in the teachers' perceptions of classroom observation when grouped according to the number of trainings they have attended. Post-hoc Dwass-Steel-Critchlow-Fligner (DSCF) pairwise comparisons further reveal that the teachers with 1–4 trainings significantly differed from those with 5–8 trainings ($p = 0.049$). Meanwhile, no significant differences were found among the other group comparisons. This suggests that exposure to professional trainings may influenced how the teachers perceived classroom observation. This is particularly true among those with fewer training experiences. This supports researches which showed that professional development and training are foundational to how the teachers engaged with evaluation tools and see them as beneficial rather than evaluative or stressful (Reños & Pontillas, 2024; Man, 2024).

In terms of years of teaching experience, the Kruskal–Wallis test yields an H value of 9.599 with a p-value of 0.008, which is less than 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. This indicates a significant difference in the teachers' perceptions of classroom observation across the different experienced groups. The post-hoc analysis shows significant differences between the teachers with 1–10 years of experience and those with 21 or more years of experience ($p = 0.009$). This applies as well to those teachers with 11–20 years of experience and those with 21 or more years of experience ($p = 0.043$). These findings suggest that the teachers with longer teaching experience tend to perceive classroom observation differently. This could possibly be due to their accumulated professional experiences, their familiarity with the evaluation systems, and their changing expectations over time. Or, this may be because the early and mid-career

teachers often gain confidence and instructional skills through structured feedback and observation while the veteran teachers might see observation as less helpful or more routine (Caranyagan & Loquere, 2025).

Indeed, researches have shown that the classroom observation can help the teachers reflect on their values and attitudes, improve their teaching practices, and grow professionally, when feedback is constructive and focused on development rather than judgment (Fayo & Hilario, 2023; Reños & Pontillas, 2024). These findings collectively suggest that both professional development opportunities and accumulated experience influence how teachers value and interpret classroom observation and its effects on their performance.

Conclusions

This study aimed to examine the teachers' perceptions of the classroom observation and its effects on their performance. The findings indicate that the teachers generally view classroom observation as a constructive process that fosters professional growth, reflective practice, and improved teaching. This is aligned with the Schön's Reflective Practice Theory which emphasizes on learning through reflection on experience. It also holds true with Vygotsky's Constructivist Theory which highlights knowledge and skills development as occurring through social interaction and guided support. While the teachers valued feedback and the collaborative nature of observations, some experienced emotional pressure and concerns about subjectivity and workload. Importantly, the teachers' positive perceptions did not significantly influence their performance ratings. This suggests that classroom observation primarily supports professional development rather than directly determining the performance outcomes. All things considered, classroom observation, when conducted fairly and is well-supported, fosters reflective practice and teaching improvement despite the challenges like emotional pressure and perceived bias.

Recommendations

Considering the results and conclusions obtained, the study recommends that:

1. The teachers should participate in at least two professional development activities each school year and prepare an Individual Development Plan (IDP) after every classroom observation to improve their instructional practices.
2. The administrators should conduct structured post-observation conferences within five working days after each classroom observation to provide clear, constructive, and actionable feedback.
3. The policy and training coordinators should develop and implement standardized classroom observation guidelines and conduct annual orientation sessions to ensure fairness, clarity, and consistency in their evaluation.
4. The curriculum developers should provide practical teaching guides and instructional toolkits aligned with the classroom observation indicators and IPCRF standards to help teachers apply feedback effectively in their instruction.

5. The other researchers should conduct further studies examining the factors influencing the teacher performance, the strategies to reduce observation-related stress, and the long-term impact of observation feedback on instructional quality.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers made sure to adhere to the established ethical standards specifically of the Ethics Committee of Foundation University to protect the respondents, who were aware of their voluntary participation in the study. Aside from that, they were also informed that they had the freedom to withdraw at any time if they wanted. Meanwhile, prior to their participation, the teacher respondents fully knew about the purpose of the study and how their responses will be utilized.

Additionally, all information collected from the teachers are kept private and confidential. The names of the respondents are not included and the results are used only for academic purposes. By completing the survey, the respondents gave their consent to be part of the study. Finally, the researchers disclose the use of AI-assisted tools, including Open AI's GPT-4, Microsoft Copilot, Gemini 3, Consensus AI and Quillbot to enhance the readability of this manuscript. After using these tools, the researchers carefully reviewed and edited the manuscript and hence take full responsibility for its content. The AI declaration is also attached in Appendix G.

Acknowledgments

The researchers sincerely thank all those who contributed to the completion of this study. They are grateful to God Almighty for His guidance and blessings. They also thank their adviser, statistician, grammarian, and panel members for their valuable support and feedback. Appreciation is extended to the school authorities, principals, and respondents for their cooperation. The researchers also thank their professors, classmates, and friends for their encouragement. Above all, they are deeply grateful to their families for their love, prayers, and support.

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